

E3UDRES2 ENT-R-E-NOVATORS PROJECT KICKOFF MEETING

The Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS) hosted on the 6th and 7th of October the kick-off meeting of the European project E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators, which aims to be one of the pillars of support of the university alliance E³UDRES² in its dimension of Research, Development and Innovation (RD&I).

In a hybrid format from the IPS campus in Setúbal, the meeting opened with a welcome from the IPS Presidency, followed by a presentation of the participants and work teams and with the intervention of Alina-Maria Bercea, responsible for the European Commission for the project. The IPS professor and researcher, Luís Coelho, who leads the coordination team, was responsible for the global presentation of the project, the details of which will be revealed over the two days of the meeting.

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators project thus brings together the six founding partners of this European consortium under construction since 2020 and will be on the ground until 2025 with the mission of surveying the conditions of research work on the extensive E³UDRES² campus - from Portugal to Latvia, passing through Hungary, Romania, Austria and Belgium.

The project is funded by the European Commission, through the Horizon Europe programme, within the framework of its pillar on scientific excellence (call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05), which aims to strengthen the research and innovation capacity of higher education institutions. countries and their ecosystems.

In these 36 months of work, the Ent-r-e-Novators project proposes to carry out a diagnosis of the existing heritage in this part of the European territory in terms of research and innovation, focusing on fundamental areas such as infrastructure, equipment and human resources, activities, RD&I lines, groups and networks, as well as Open Science policies and practices and engagement with society.

The expected results of the project are the joint development of strategies, associated with five different transformation modules, as well as the execution of the respective pilot programs, in order to "unlock our potential for excellence in research and innovation, to accelerate the transformation in a European Multi-institutional Research and Innovation Center for Smart and Sustainable Regions", says the projects' coordination team.

In this process of building a common RD&I agenda, the main goal is to boost research from and to the regions involved - which is in the DNA of E³UDRES² - not only by reinforcing the cooperation of higher education institutions (HEIs) with the environment, working on more integrated and long-term cooperation models, as well as greater proximity and involvement of citizens, transforming HEIs into more open and connected institutions.

